

TEACHERS ENGAGED IN ONLINE BUSINESS IN RELATION TO JOB PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the relationship between teachers' perceptions of online business and their job performance in Ubay I, II, and III Districts, Division of Bohol, for the academic year 2020-2021. The research aimed to understand the profiles of teacher-respondents engaged in online business, their perceptions towards online business across various contexts, and the impact of these perceptions on their job performance. Key areas explored include the demographic profile of respondents, their assessment of online business in technological, organizational, environmental, and beneficial contexts, and the effect of their online business activities on teaching skills, management skills, discipline/regularity, and interpersonal relations. The study found that while teachers generally perform well across all job performance dimensions, with high ratings in teaching skills, management skills, discipline/regularity, and interpersonal relations, there was no significant relationship between demographic factors and job performance. However, significant relationships were found between perceptions of online business and job performance, particularly in terms of discipline/regularity and overall performance. Based on these findings, the study recommends enhancing support and training for teachers, promoting positive perceptions of online business, implementing monitoring and evaluation systems, addressing issues of discipline and regularity, encouraging long-term engagement in online business, and conducting further research to explore additional influencing factors. These recommendations aim to support teachers in balancing their online business activities with their professional responsibilities, ultimately enhancing their job performance and contributing to more effective teaching environments.

Keywords: *Discipline, E-business, Job performance, Online business, and Perceptions*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought about significant changes in various aspects of life, including the way people engage in economic activities. As the world continues to recover, individuals, including the aging population, have increasingly turned to online platforms for buying and selling goods, utilizing social media and other digital tools to sustain their livelihoods. This shift has led to a burgeoning online retail environment where even government employees, such as teachers, have started to participate in online business ventures.

As noted by Ablaña and Isidro (2015), the pressures of modern society—characterized by complex social, economic, and political challenges—demand that government employees adopt innovative strategies to meet these demands. Despite being employed, many workers still struggle to escape poverty, with estimates from the International Labour Organization (ILO) suggesting that up to 40% of workers globally earn less than the poverty line of \$2 or ₱100 per day (Melamed, Hartwig, & Grant, 2011). In the Philippines, where the government is the largest employer, teachers play a crucial role in ensuring the functionality of the education system (Ablaña et al., 2015).

Job satisfaction is a critical factor influencing teachers' commitment and productivity within school organizations. Satisfied teachers are more likely to be engaged and committed to their work, leading to better participation and overall performance (Shila & Sevilla, 2015; Sadasa, 2013). However, job satisfaction is closely linked to work compensation, which in turn affects teaching performance (Baluyos, Rivera, & Baluyos, 2019). Given the economic challenges exacerbated by the pandemic, many teachers have sought additional income through online businesses, raising questions about the potential impact of these activities on their job performance.

The working environment plays a vital role in maintaining staff motivation and productivity. A poor working environment can lead to decreased job satisfaction, ultimately affecting performance (Ozgen & Yalcin, 2010). Institutions must strive to improve the quality of work life to foster a productive and motivated workforce (Solmus, 2011). The relationship between job performance and factors such as job satisfaction, work environment, and compensation has been well-documented (Motowidlo, 2011; Rao & Kumar, 2014). However, the rise of online business activities among teachers presents a new variable that warrants investigation.

Teachers' job performance is influenced by various factors, including their knowledge, responsibility, and the teaching environment (Rao & Kumar, 2014). Leigh and Mead (2015) highlighted the decline in teaching quality due to outdated preparation and stagnant compensation schemes. Hakanen, Bakker, and Schaufeli (2011) introduced the Job Demands–Resources Model, suggesting that job performance is affected by both job demands (e.g., burnout, ill health) and job resources (e.g., engagement, commitment). Understanding the balance between these factors is essential for improving teacher performance.

Lambert (2014) emphasized that factors such as mindset, immersion in different environments, and reflective practice can significantly enhance job performance. Additionally, passion for teaching, as described by Vallerand (2010), can drive motivation and job satisfaction, leading to improved performance. Ho, Wong, and Lee (2011) found that harmonious passion positively correlates with job performance, mediated by cognitive absorption.

Given the complexities of these dynamics, this study aims to investigate the relationship between teachers' engagement in online business activities and their job performance in the Ubay I, II, and III Districts during the School Year 2020-2021. By exploring these variables, the study seeks to provide insights into how teachers balance their professional responsibilities with external economic activities, and how this balance affects their overall job performance.

Research Questions

The main thrust of the study was to determine teachers' perception towards online business in relation to job performance in Ubay I, II, and III Districts, Division of Bohol of the School Year 2020-2021. The findings of this study served as bases for proposing sustainability plan.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher- respondents engaged in online business in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4. teaching experience;
 - 1.5. online business platform/s; and
 - 1.6. years in online business?

2. What is the perception of the respondents towards online business in terms of:
 - 2.1. technological context;
 - 2.2. organizational context;
 - 2.3. environmental context;
 - 2.4. beneficial context?

3. What is the respondents' assessment on the job performance of teachers engaged in online business towards their:
 - 3.1. teaching skills;
 - 3.2. management skills;
 - 3.3. discipline/ regularity; and
 - 3.4. interpersonal relations?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' job performance and their profile?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' perception towards online business and job performance in terms of:
 - 5.1. teaching skills;
 - 5.2. management skills;
 - 5.3. discipline/ regularity; and
 - 5.4. interpersonal relations?

6. On the bases of the findings of the study, what sustainability program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This section focused on the methodology that was utilized in the conduct of the study. It also outlined the research design, the procedure that was followed, the process of collecting the data, and the analysis. During the collection process, the ethical considerations were also discussed.

Research Design

This study employs a quantitative correlational research design, utilizing a questionnaire as the primary method for data collection. The correlational approach was chosen to examine the relationship between engagement in online business activities and job performance.

Research Environment and Research Participants

This study was conducted in the second congressional district of Bohol, specifically in the Ubay I, Ubay II, and Ubay III districts. These locations are situated in the northeastern part of Bohol Province and form a zone district under the Department of Education (DepEd). A total of 30 elementary schools from these districts were included in the research.

The research subjects were selected through purposive sampling, comprising 10 elementary schools per district. The sample included 76 teachers engaged in online business and 30 elementary school heads, resulting in a total of 106 respondents who were actively serving during the 2020-2021 school year. The distribution of respondents is presented in Table A.

Table A
Distribution of Respondents

Name of Schools	Teachers with Online Business	School Heads	Total
I. Ubay I District			
1. Ubay Central Elementary School	4	1	5
2. Fatima Elementary School	2	1	3
3. Camambugan Elementary School	4	1	5
4. Tapal Elementary School	2	1	3
5. Humay-humay Elementary School	3	1	4
6 . Bood Elementary School	2	1	3
7. Calanggaman Elementary School	3	1	4

8. Sentinela Elementary School	2	1	3
9. Tapon Elementary School	3	1	4
10. Achila Elementary School	2	1	3
II. Ubay II District			
1. Biabas Central Elementary School	3	1	4
2. Juagdan Elementary School	3	1	4
3. San Vicente Elementary School	2	1	3
4. Benliw Elementary School	2	1	3
5. Union Elementary School	2	1	3
6. Tipolo Elementary School	5	1	6
7. Imelda Elementary School	3	1	4
8. Sinandigan Elementary School	3	1	4
9. Guintaboan Elementary School	2	1	3
10. Cagting Elementary School	3	1	4
III. Ubay III District			
1. San Pascual Central Elementary School	3	1	4
2. Bulilis Elementary School	2	1	3
3. Hambabauran Elementary School	2	1	3
4. Gabi Elementary School	2	1	3
5. Casate Elementary School	2	1	3
6. Pag-asa Elementary School	2	1	3
7. California Elementary School	1	1	2
8. Bay-ang Elementary School	2	1	3
9. Ilihan Elementary School	2	1	3
10. Lomangog Elementary School	3	1	4
Grand Total	76	30	106

Research Instrument

To assess teachers' perceptions of online business and its impact on job performance in Ubay I, II, and III Districts for the 2020-2021 School Year, a modified questionnaire was used. This questionnaire was structured into three sections: the first section collected demographic data, the second section evaluated the impact of online business on operational, managerial, strategic, and beneficial aspects, and the third section measured job performance using a 4-point Likert scale across four dimensions: teaching skills, management skills, discipline/regularity, and interpersonal relations. The instruments used were adapted and validated to ensure their reliability and relevance.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first secured approval from the Dean of the College of Advanced Studies and obtained an official permit from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Department of Education for the Ubay I, II, and III Districts. Additionally, permission was sought from the School Heads of each institution and the teachers involved in the study. Questionnaires were personally distributed to the respondents, who were given a thorough explanation of the study's purpose. Assistance was provided to clarify any difficult words or questions, and respondents were allowed sufficient time to complete the questionnaires.

Following data collection, the responses were tallied, tabulated, and collated. The data were then analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics to address the specific research questions.

Data Analysis

To determine the demographic profile of the teachers, perceived online business, and level of job performance of teachers; the Percentage, Weighted Mean, Chi-Square, and Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient were used.

6. To determine the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, percentage was used.

Formula:

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100$$

Where:

P = percentage

F = frequency of responses

N = number of cases

2. To determine the perception of the teachers with online business, and teachers' job performance, the weighted mean was used.

Formula:

$$WM = \frac{\sum f(x)}{N}$$

Where:

WM = weighted mean

$\sum f(x)$ = summation of frequency of scale value x

N = number of cases

Composite Mean. The same scale will be used in interpreting the composite weight means:

$$\frac{\text{Sum of Weight Means}}{\text{Number of Items}}$$

3. To determine the significant degree of relationship between the teachers' job performance and their profile, the data were subjected to Chi-Square test.

Formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(f_o - f_e)^2}{f_e}$$

Where:

χ^2 = correlation coefficient

f_o = observed frequency

f_e = expected frequency

The obtained Chi-Square ratio was checked against the Table of Significant values at 0 .05 level.

4. Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the degree of correlation between the perceived online business as to teaching performance of teachers with the formula:

Formula:

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum D^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

Where:

r_s = Spearman rank Correlation Coefficient

$\frac{\sum D^2}{n}$ = sum of the squares of the difference between rank x and rank y

n = sample size

6 = constant

RESULTS

This chapter covers with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the gathered data was to determine the teachers' online business in relation to job performance in Ubay I, II, and III Districts, Division of Bohol of the School Year 2020-2021.

Table 1
Profile of Teachers Engaged in Online Business
N=76

1.1 Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
25 years old and below	0	0.00	
26-30 years old	15	19.74	2
31-35 years old	54	71.05	1
36 years old and above	7	9.21	3
Total	76	100%	
1.2 Sex			
Male	1	1.32	2
Female	75	98.68	1
Total	76	100%	
1.3 Highest Educational Attainment			
Bachelor Degree Holder	1	1.32	2
With units in Master's Degree	75	98.68	1
MA Graduate/ With PhD Units/ Doctorate	0	0.00	3
Total	76	100%	
1.4 Teaching Experience			
5 years and below	1	1.32	4
6-10 years	15	19.74	2
11-15 years	51	67.10	1
16 years and above	9	11.84	3
Total	76	100%	
1.5 Online Business Platform/s (Social Media)			
Facebook	76	100.00	1

Twitter	0	0.00	
Instagram	0	0.00	
Others	0	0.00	
Total	76	100%	
1.6 Years in Online Business			
Below 1 year	39	51.32	1
1-2 years	12	15.79	3
3 years and above	25	32.89	2
Total	76	100%	

Table 1 presents the profile of teachers engaged in online business. The majority of these teachers (71.05%) are between 31 and 35 years old, indicating that this middle age group is most active in online business. The study shows a significant gender imbalance, with 98.68% of the respondents being female, suggesting that online business is predominantly undertaken by women in this group. In terms of education, nearly all respondents (98.68%) have completed coursework towards a Master's Degree, highlighting a high level of educational attainment. Most teachers (67.10%) have 11 to 15 years of teaching experience, with no teachers having over 21 years of experience in online business, suggesting a preference for those with moderate experience. All respondents use Facebook as their primary online business platform, underscoring its importance and dominance in their business activities. Finally, over half of the respondents (51.32%) have been engaged in online business for less than one year, while 32.89% have been involved for three years or more, indicating a mix of new and more established online entrepreneurs among the teachers.

Table 2
Perception of the Respondents Towards Online Business
N₁= 76; N₂=30

Statement	Teachers		School Heads		Overall		
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	Rank
2.1 Technological Context							
1. Online business is a great benefit to my product.	3.54	SA	3.77	SA	3.66	SA	1
2. ICT is compatible with the way we do business.	3.70	SA	3.13	A	3.42	SA	4
3. Overall, using online business is easy for me.	3.36	SA	3.90	SA	3.63	SA	2
4. The cost of using online business is low.	3.07	A	3.68	SA	3.38	A	5
5. I can communicate others to buy using online business.	3.54	SA	3.42	SA	3.48	SA	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.44	SA	3.58	SA	3.51	Strongly Agree	
2.2 Organizational Context							
1. I have the skills needed to do online business.	3.50	SA	3.52	SA	3.51	SA	3
2. I have sufficient financial resources to implement online business in business operations.	3.79	SA	3.71	SA	3.75	SA	1
3. I emphasize research and development (R&D), technological leadership, and innovation as I do online business.	3.24	A	3.48	SA	3.36	SA	5
4. I have a clear plan regarding the use of online business.	3.67	SA	3.61	SA	3.64	SA	2
5. I have a clear standard operating procedures (SOP) in running a business.	3.59	SA	3.32	SA	3.46	SA	4
Average Weighted Mean	3.57	SA	3.53	SA	3.54	Strongly Agree	
2.3. Environmental Context							
1. Our customers and / or business competitors encourage us to implement online business.	3.53	SA	3.48	SA	3.51	SA	2.5

2. The government is actively providing various facilities to support the application of online business.	3.54	SA	3.52	SA	3.53	SA	1
3. Telecommunications infrastructure (such as the internet network or electronic payments) is reliable to support the use of online business.	3.30	SA	3.71	SA	3.51	SA	2.5
Average Weighted Mean (AWM)	3.45	SA	3.57	SA	3.52	Strongly Agree	
2.4. Beneficial Context							
1. Increased business productivity.	3.82	SA	3.35	SA	3.59	SA	3
2. Reduced business costs.	3.64	SA	3.74	SA	3.69	SA	1
3. Creates better management of resources (e.g, inventory, human resources, etc.	3.25	SA	3.55	SA	3.40	SA	4
4. Helps me earn extra income other than my salary.	3.87	SA	3.39	SA	3.63	SA	2
5. Helps me pay expenses at home.	3.49	SA	3.10	A	3.30	SA	5
Average Weighted Mean	3.61	SA	3.43	SA	3.52	Strongly Agree	
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.52	SA	3.53	SA	3.53	Strongly Agree	

Legend:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Interpretation	Weighted Mean (WM)
3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	
2.50 – 3.24	Agree (A)	
1.75 – 2.49	Disagree (DA)	
1.00 – 1.74	Strongly Disagree (SDA)	

Table 2 indicates that respondents generally view online business positively. In the technological context, "Online business is a great benefit to my product" received the highest mean of 3.66, while "The cost of using online business is low" had the lowest mean of 3.38, both reflecting strong agreements. In the organizational context, the highest mean of 3.75 for "I have sufficient financial resources to implement online business" shows strong confidence in financial readiness. The environmental context highlighted significant government support with a mean of 3.53 for "The government is actively providing various facilities to support the application of online business," and the beneficial context identified "Reduced business costs" as a major advantage with a mean of 3.69. Overall, the average mean across all contexts is 3.53, demonstrating a strong overall agreement on the positive impact of online business.

Table 3
Respondents' Assessment on Job Performance of Teachers Engaged in Online Business
N₁= 76; N₂=30

Statement	Teachers		School Heads		Overall		
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	Rank
3.1 Teaching Skills							
1. Apply a variety of instructional materials aside from Learning	3.72	O	3.71	O	3.72	O	2.5
2. Activity Sheets and Modules provided by the department.							
3. A good number of the pupils in my class get good grades applying blended modality learning.	3.76	O	3.68	O	3.72	O	2.5
4. Going to school fully prepared for the instructions to parents during distribution and retrievals of LAS/LM.	3.47	O	3.27	O	3.37	O	4
5. Difficult topics are made easy by contextualizing the different activities.	3.30	O	3.16	VS	3.23	VS	5
6. Provided various interventions to pupils to meet their learning needs by including in the Weekly Home Learning Plan.	3.72	O	3.90	O	3.81	O	1
Average Weighted Mean	3.60	O	3.54	O	3.57	Outstanding	

3.2 Management Skills							
1. In addition to teaching, I also accomplish other tasks in schools.	3.93	O	3.77	O	3.85	O	1
2. Clerical duties do not interfere in my job as a teacher.	3.75	O	3.10	VS	3.43	O	4
3. Home problems do not interfere in my job as a teacher.	3.29	O	3.48	O	3.39	O	5
4. Quickly adjust when there is a change in my responsibilities.	3.53	O	3.55	O	3.54	O	3
5. Do all in my power to advance my performance.	3.34	O	3.84	O	3.59	O	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.57	O	3.55	O	3.56	Outstanding	
3.3 Discipline/Regularity							
1. I am always punctual to school.	3.55	O	3.19	VS	3.37	O	3
2. Commence work on time.	3.70	O	3.74	O	3.72	O	1
3. Avoid irrelevant activities during my onsite works.	3.46	O	3.68	O	3.57	O	5
4. I am completing the instruction / directives on time.	3.49	O	3.26	O	3.38	O	4
5. Control and maintain promptness of pupils LAS/LM submission.	3.59	O	3.29	O	3.44	O	2
Average Weighted Mean (AWM)	3.56	O	3.43	O	3.50	Outstanding	
3.4 Interpersonal Relations							
1. My relationship with my colleagues is cordial.	3.96	O	3.61	O	3.79	O	1
2. Solve students' problems outside teaching specially in their written/performance output.	3.51	O	3.35	O	3.43	O	4
3. Cooperate with other teachers while doing my job.	3.43	O	3.26	O	3.35	O	5
4. To advance my pupils learning, I also relate effectively with their parents by giving clear direction in Weekly Home Learning Plan.	3.53	O	3.65	O	3.59	O	2
5. Assist the school head to solve our school problems like issues and concerns on Distant Learning Modality.	3.71	O	3.32	O	3.52	O	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.63	O	3.44	O	3.54	Outstanding	
Overall Average Weighted Mean	3.59	O	3.49	O	3.54	Outstanding	

Legend

Rating Scale	Verbal Interpretation	Weighted Mean (WM)
3.25 – 4.00	Outstanding (O)	
2.50 – 3.24	Very Satisfactory (VS)	
1.75 – 2.49	Satisfactory (S)	
1.00 – 1.74	Poor (P)	

Table 3 assesses the job performance of teachers engaged in online business across four key areas: teaching skills, management skills, discipline/regularity, and interpersonal relations. The data reveals that teachers excel particularly in providing interventions for pupils, with a weighted mean of 3.81 in teaching skills. In management skills, they demonstrate strong performance in handling additional tasks, scoring 3.85. Discipline and punctuality are also strong, with a mean of 3.72 for starting work on time. Lastly, interpersonal relations are marked by cordial relationships with colleagues, achieving a mean of 3.79. Overall, the average weighted mean across all areas is 3.54, indicating an outstanding level of job performance.

Table 4
Relationship Between the Teachers' Job Performance and Their Profile
N = 76

Teachers Job Performance and their Profile as to...	X ²	df	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Age	1.677	2	0.432	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Sex	6.688	1	0.010	Significant	Reject H ₀
Highest Educational Attainment	0.154	1	0.695	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Teaching Experience	0.886	3	0.829	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀

Number of Years in Online Business	3.926	2	0.140	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
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*Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 4 examines the relationship between teachers' job performance and their profile characteristics. The analysis shows that job performance is not significantly related to age, highest educational attainment, teaching experience, or number of years in online business, as indicated by p-values of 0.432, 0.695, 0.829, and 0.140, respectively. In contrast, there is a significant relationship between job performance and sex, with a p-value of 0.010. This implies that gender differences impact job performance, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis in this case.

Table 5
Relationship Between the Teachers' Perception Towards Online Business and Job Performance
N = 76

Teachers' Perception Towards Online Business and Job Performance as to...	r	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Teaching Skills	-0.047	0.685	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Management Skills	-0.172	0.137	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Discipline/regularity	0.276	0.016	Significant	Reject H ₀
Interpersonal relations	0.211	0.067	Not Significant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Overall Job Performance	0.812	<.001	Significant	Reject H₀

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 5 analyzes the relationship between teachers' perceptions of online business and their job performance. The data reveals that perceptions of teaching skills, management skills, and interpersonal relations do not significantly impact job performance, with p-values of 0.685, 0.137, and 0.067, respectively. However, perceptions of discipline/regularity have a significant relationship with job performance (p-value = 0.016), indicating that regularity and discipline influence job performance. Additionally, the overall job performance shows a strong significant correlation (p-value < 0.001), suggesting a robust association between general perceptions of online business and overall job performance.

DISCUSSION

Findings

The data gathered were then analyzed and interpreted and after a thorough and careful analysis of gathered data, the researchers' arrived at the following valuable findings:

The research findings provide a comprehensive view of the respondents' profiles, perceptions, and job performance. Among the 76 teacher-respondents, the majority are aged 31-35 years and are predominantly female. Most have pursued graduate-level education, with 67.10% having 11 to 15 years of teaching experience. Facebook is the universal platform used for online business, and over half have been engaged in it for less than a year. Regarding perceptions of online business, respondents show strong agreement across all contexts: technological, organizational, environmental, and beneficial, with an overall average mean of 3.53. In terms of job performance, teachers excel in teaching skills, management skills, discipline/regularity, and interpersonal relations, each category rated as "Outstanding," with an overall mean of 3.54. Analysis reveals no significant relationship between teachers' profiles and job performance in areas such as age, education, teaching experience, or online business duration. However, significant relationships are found between perceptions of online business and job performance in terms of discipline/regularity and overall performance, though not for teaching skills, management skills, or interpersonal relations.

Conclusions

Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that teachers engaged in online business demonstrate a high level of job performance across various dimensions, including teaching skills, management skills, discipline/regularity, and interpersonal relations. The strong agreement in their perceptions of online business across technological, organizational, environmental, and beneficial contexts underscores its perceived value and positive impact on their professional roles. Despite these favorable views and high-performance ratings, the study reveals no significant relationship between demographic factors and job performance, suggesting that factors such as age, educational attainment, and teaching experience do not significantly influence the effectiveness of teachers' job performance in this context. However, there is significant evidence that perceptions of online business are related to job performance, particularly in terms of discipline/regularity and overall performance. This highlights the importance of a positive perception of online business in enhancing teachers' professional effectiveness, although it does not uniformly impact all aspects of job performance.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Enhance Support and Training.** Given the positive impact of teachers' perceptions on their job performance, it is recommended to provide targeted support and training that further enhances their skills in online business. This can include professional development programs focused on integrating online business practices with teaching, as well as workshops on effective online business management.

2. **Promote Positive Perceptions.** Schools and educational institutions should actively promote and support positive perceptions of online business among teachers. This can be achieved through regular communication about the benefits and successes of online business, as well as by providing resources and incentives that highlight its value in enhancing professional performance.
3. **Monitor and Evaluate.** Implement regular monitoring and evaluation systems to assess the impact of online business on teachers' job performance. This should include feedback mechanisms to identify areas for improvement and to ensure that the online business practices are effectively supporting teachers' professional roles.
4. **Address Disciplinary and Regularity Issues.** Since discipline and regularity are significantly related to job performance, schools should focus on strategies to address and improve these areas. This might involve developing clear guidelines and support systems to help teachers manage their time and responsibilities effectively.
5. **Encourage Long-term Engagement.** Given the high percentage of teachers with less than a year of online business experience, it is important to encourage long-term engagement. Providing ongoing support and fostering a community of practice can help teachers build sustained online business practices that contribute positively to their job performance.
6. **Further Research.** Conduct further research to explore other potential factors that may influence the relationship between online business perceptions and job performance. This could include examining the impact of specific online business strategies and tools, as well as the role of external support systems.

By implementing these recommendations, educational institutions can better support teachers in integrating online business practices, ultimately enhancing their overall job performance and contributing to more effective teaching environments.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without coercion. No harm came to participants, and the study received ethics committee approval. Researchers declared no conflicts of interest and reported findings transparently and honestly. Cultural sensitivity was respected throughout the research process.

PROPOSED SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

Rationale

The primary goal of education is to facilitate learning, and the environment where teaching and learning occur significantly impacts the quality of this learning experience (Hasbay, 2018). Job satisfaction is crucial for ensuring teachers' commitment and productivity within a school organization. Satisfied teachers are more likely to be engaged and committed, enhancing their overall job performance (Shila et al., 2015; Sadasa, 2013). Job satisfaction is thus a fundamental requirement for effective work performance (Baluyos et al., 2019).

In recent years, e-business has evolved rapidly, driven by technological innovations that present new opportunities. This shift involves transforming traditional business models and adapting to new competitive landscapes. E-business now involves various structural patterns, including e-channels, click-and-brick models, e-portals, e-market makers, and mobile portals (Putra et al., 2020).

Given these dynamics, and based on the findings and conclusions, a sustainability plan is proposed to balance teachers' online business activities with their job performance.

Objectives

This program aims to:

1. Conduct a virtual re-orientation for teachers engaged in online business, focusing on the DECS Manual 2000 handbook and the Code of Ethical Standards for Teachers, particularly concerning discipline and regularity.
2. Enhance the morale of teachers involved in online business.
3. Monitor the performance of teachers engaged in online business.

Mechanics of Implementation

With approval from the examining tribunal, the researcher will present the proposal to the district supervisors of Ubay I, Ubay II, and Ubay III Districts. Feedback, suggestions, or recommendations will be incorporated to tailor the plan to specific needs.

Schedule of Implementation

The program will be presented during the Summer Assessment and INSET sessions in June, and the implementation will commence in the subsequent school year.

Monitoring and Evaluation System

A monitoring and evaluation tool will be developed to assess the effects of the sustainability program. This system will facilitate continuous improvement and refinement of the plan to ensure its effectiveness.

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